

Lucerna Manual # 2:

How to Catalogue *Slide Sets* and *Slides* in Lucerna

(Version May 2018)

First of all, thank you for your help in the Lucerna project and for making the time and effort to share your information on lantern slide sets with the magic lantern community!

Before you start inserting data please read the background information. If you have any suggestions for improvement for either Lucerna or this manual, if you have questions, or if this manual needs clarification, please contact us via the form on the Lucerna Website.

What this manual is about

This manual is split in two parts:

Part 1 gives background information on the way that Lucerna works, definitions we use and common problems that occur when determining the information about lantern slides and slide sets.

Part 2 is a step-by-step manual which shows you how to insert data about lantern slides and lantern slide sets.

This manual focusses on information relevant to cataloguing slides and slide sets. Drop-down menus sometimes have more options that are not discussed here as they are not relevant to cataloguing slide sets and slides. If you are curious about these options, you will find additional explanations in the red info buttons which appear next to each entry field when you are logged in.

What this manual is not about

This manual does not give detailed information about inserting data in the other main sections: People, Organisations, Events, Locations, Hardware, Texts, Keywords or Collections. We have not, as yet, created manuals for the above-mentioned entities. However, as the principle is similar, we hope that the descriptions given here are helpful and that you feel enabled to adapt these guidelines in order to insert

information on other types of data. Please contact us if you want to contribute to Lucerna's lantern hardware section and need more information.

This manual does not give a detailed account of how to use Lucerna for inventorying a collection of slides. We are currently working on a separate manual that pays detailed attention to cataloguing from a collection's point of view. In brief: to catalogue a collection, you first need to follow the guidelines given in this manual, i.e. catalogue the slide sets and, in a second step, link the slide sets and slides to the relevant collection. Please contact us if you want to use Lucerna for cataloguing a collection and need more information.

Part 1

1.1 Some Background Information on Lucerna

The way that you see and make sense of the information on slide sets or references on printed paper is not necessarily the way that databases (and Lucerna) work. Some links between the data and its meaning might seem intuitively obvious to you, but they may not be obvious to other users of Lucerna.

Lucerna's aim is ambitious: to gather all information about the magic lantern and make it available to everyone who shares an interest in the magic lantern and the various facets of its use. Anyone can search and read the data in the Lucerna database. Lucerna is used by private collectors, lanternists, archivists, museum curators, family historians, social historians, media scholars, collectors of scientific instruments, people with an interest in Victorian culture, visual artists and more. This means that *every* piece of information – even information that is irrelevant to you – might be relevant to other people's interests and questions.

The more information each contributor adds, the more Lucerna will be of value to all; we would therefore appreciate it if you input data as comprehensively as possible.

Lucerna is a reference database and a research resource, not a catalogue of a specific collection. Its aim is to document and illustrate the lantern's heritage through its various histories over time covering production, distribution, exhibition and reception. Lantern slides and lantern hardware are important artefacts.

Neither Lucerna nor the institution hosting Lucerna own the objects of which we have digital images or the texts from which the information is derived. These objects are owned by our contributing libraries, archives, museums and individuals and the copyright for each image is always indicated. It also means that several examples of the same slide can be found in (and hence connected to) various collections.

1.2 How to Insert Information on Slide Sets into Lucerna

This manual guides you through inserting data about *slide sets* and *slides*. The information you have may come from different sources, most likely from trade catalogues or the slides themselves. We start from the assumption that you know at least the title of a slide set or can allocate a title by looking at the slide set in front of you.

1.3 What is Defined as a Slide Set in Lucerna

Basically, in Lucerna, all slides are considered to be part of a slide set. Because all lantern shows we know of consist of more than one image and slides were usually issued in sets, we regard every slide as part of a set. In some cases (explained below) slide sets may consist of only one slide. Sets may be put together by the artist, the lecturer, or pre-assembled by a manufacturer.

- **Lantern slides produced and sold in sets by the manufacturer or distributor** comprise by far the most in numbers of all produced lantern slides. Most of them were produced and distributed in the heyday of the magic lantern between 1880 and 1910. Slide sets can consist of 1 to more than 300 individual slides.

- **Panoramic Slides** (rectangular slides with either more than one image upon the artefact or slides that show a panorama of which only parts are shown in projection) are regarded as a slide set. They can be either produced as an individual slide (in that case the slide set consists of 1 slide) or come in a set of more than one panoramic slide if listed as such in a catalogue.

- **Slide sets produced by amateurs** are considered slide sets as well. From the 1890s onwards, manufacturers and distributors offered their services to private individuals and produced lantern slides from the photographic negatives of amateur photographers. Sets we know of show festive family scenes, document the work of a

local association or camera club, or were produced by teachers and lecturers who copied graphic material from text books. In our definition, sets produced by amateurs are characterised by not having been in public or commercial circulation and distribution networks. If you enter data on an amateur slide set, please choose “privately made” in the tab “organisation”.

- **Dissolving views** are a set of two, three or more slides that are meant to be dissolved into each other. Well-known examples include a windmill with changing seasons or day-to-night changes.

- **Individual Magic Lantern Slides** that were not produced as sets but were produced, marketed and sold as individual objects. Such slides are considered a slide set, consisting of one slide. An example of lantern slide sets that consist of one slide are most chromatropes or slipping slides.

If, however, a catalogue advertised a set of slipping slides, then you should consider the entirety of all individual slipping slides or chromatropes as one set. This is the preferred solution.

We suggest that you group slides into slide sets with attributed titles, e.g.

“Chromatropes by Newton” or “slipping slides in toy format” as this facilitates searching.

- **Orphan Slides:** If you have a slide and cannot attribute it to anything else in Lucerna, you can upload it as an individual slide – until future evidence tells us more about it. Here, again, we suggest that you group slides into slide sets with attributed titles, e.g. “miscellaneous sea shells” or “unidentified microscopic photographs”.

1.4 What is not a Slide Set in Lucerna

- **Slides that are assembled in a box** are sometimes considered “slide sets” and sometimes considered a “collection”. This depends upon the slides in the box. The first step to choose the correct entity is to identify what you have got.

If a box in a museum or in your attic is a mix of several commercially produced slides that were originally produced as distinct slide sets, then you should attribute the individual slides in your collection to the relevant commercially produced slide sets that they come from (and catalogue them as such). In a second step, you can connect the relevant slides of the slide sets to your collection. During this step, you can add your museum’s accession number, box number etc. so the historical coherency of the

collection is not lost. See, for example, the way that the slide collection of Manchester Museum has been catalogued (Lucerna ID number 2500064).

Only in the case that the items in a box form a unique set of amateur production, or if you cannot identify the slides in a box as part of a distributed slide set, the “collection” and the “slide set” conflate. In this case, you can define the content of a box as “slide set” and mark it as attributed title (see, for example, the slide sets of Museum Sonnenborgh (Lucerna ID number 2500365).

We will write a manual on how to use Lucerna for cataloguing collections in the near future. Please contact us if you want to use Lucerna for cataloguing your collection and wish further assistance.

- The actual projected slides of a Magic Lantern Show. From numbering and annotations and the practice of present-day lanternists, we know that actual lantern shows were not always a mere projection of the set, as the distributor sold them. Lanternists and performers combined individual slides or slides from different sets freely. If you know about the programming of certain slides in a show, you can enter the data as slide sets and choose “privately assembled” in the tab “organisation” and give the title of the event as title of the slide set (e.g. if the program was titled “The Salvation’s Army Christmas Matinee 1902” the title for both the event and slide set would be “Salvation Army’s Christmas Matinee 1902”). The logic behind this is similar to cataloguing collections.

- Slides grouped by the assembler according to a specific logic

Sometimes, collectors and performers assemble or document slides according to a specific logic. In this case, you should catalogue these slides as a slide set and chose “privately assembled” in the tab “organisation”. An example of such a case is the slide set “Sunny Memories” (Lucerna ID number 3008685).

1.5 Common Sources for the Identification of Slide Sets

The most common sources for identifying slide sets are the individual slides of the slide sets themselves, catalogues of lantern slide manufacturers, distributors and annexes in catalogues of lanterns, advertisements, and the boxes (wooden or cardboard) in which the slide sets were sold.

Note: When you are looking for catalogues in Lucerna, click the text button. In the field “Type of text:” choose “catalogue”, and in the “Online digital copy available?” choose “only show texts with an online digital copy”.

Individual Slides of Slide Sets

Advantages:

- Individual slides commonly carry information on the face and edge of the slide. This can range from as little as a slide number to as much as the slide title, the slide set's title, the slide's number within the set, and sometimes the manufacturer's logo or the artist's name.
- Individual slides inform about the type of image and production process.
- Some individual slides of slide sets are neatly and unambiguously titled – the slide set's name, the order number of the slide in the set and, in some cases, the titles of the individual slides are readable.

Disadvantages:

- The individual slides of the slide sets are not always titled, or they may carry different numbers (the manufacturer's number and the number of the slide in a particular show are often found next to each other on a slide).
- It may be unclear at which point in time handwritten notes were made, whether the handwriting belongs to the distributor, manufacturer or was added later by somebody else.
- It is not clear whether label and logo belong to a manufacturer or a distributor.

Catalogues of Lantern Slide Manufacturers

Advantages:

- Catalogues link the title to the manufacturer and mostly list the titles of the individual slides as part of the set. They sometimes give information on the type of image (photographic, hand-painted) and the price of a set.

Disadvantages:

- Catalogues of Lantern Slide manufacturers are often undated.
- Some later manufacturers took over the stock from previous manufacturers without mentioning the original publishing date or manufacturer.

Catalogues of Lantern Slide Distributors, Annexes in Catalogues for Lanterns

Advantages:

- As with catalogues of lantern slide manufacturers, these catalogues link the title to the manufacturer and mostly list the titles of the individual slides as

part of the set. They sometimes give information on the type of image (photographic, hand-painted).

- Some catalogues include sale or rental prices.

Disadvantages:

- Catalogues of distributors do not usually mention the manufacturer of the slide set.
- In some cases, distributors use wrong titles or invent their own titles.
- Distributors usually translate the title if the set was originally produced by a manufacturer in another country, without reference to the original title or manufacturer.

Advertisements or Short Lists by Lantern Manufactures and Distributors

Advantages:

- Advertisements provide information on the distributor or manufacturer and help in dating the slide sets. They feature the title.

Disadvantages:

- Most short lists or advertisements only give the title of the set but do not always provide information on the number of slides or the titles of the individual slides.

Boxes (wooden or cardboard) in which the Slide Sets were sold and shipped

Advantages:

- Boxes indicate the format of the slides, the number and which distributor's or manufacturer's stock they were in.
- A price can sometimes be found on the box.

Disadvantages:

- Even when a price is marked on the box, it may not be clear whether this is the manufacturer's, distributor's or collector's price.
- Distributors may use wrong titles or might translate the titles freely.
- The box may be an original but the current contents of the box may be unrelated.

1.6 Common Difficulties in Entering Data about Slides Sets and Slides

Dating and titling the material are amongst the most difficult aspects of putting together information of slide sets, especially when adding information derived from an individual slide.

Once you become familiar with lantern slides, and can deduce information from the different styles of masks, writings and the numbering style of different slide manufacturers, you will find it easy to attribute a slide set to a manufacturer. We trust your expertise and invite you to share the information. Please enter your reasons and conclusions in the field “public notes” (visible to all users) or “researcher notes” (only visible to logged-in users) as they might be helpful to others.

If the title is not written directly on the slides of the slide set, then you may find the title by looking at a manufacturer’s catalogue, comparing that description with the actual image and seeing if it matches. If you do not have a catalogue at hand and cannot find entries in Lucerna, please send us an email. We hold some information that we have not yet been able to upload to Lucerna, which may help you to reduce ambiguities.

Please note: if you have doubts about which slide set you have before you and who the maker was, try searching in various ways and always check carefully before entering the data. The Lucerna manuals do not give information on how to interpret the information on individual slides in a way that you can attribute a slide set to a manufacturer. If you want to find out about this, we invite you to contact the Magic Lantern Society <http://www.magiclantern.org.uk>

You can insert data from a slide set without knowing its official title if you can make sense of the images. For example, if from looking at them you can say that this is about “Little Red Riding Hood” or “Astronomy plates” or “Views from Italy”, you can still create an entry by choosing “allocated title”. This is further explained in part 2 of this manual. The set title that you allocate will automatically be displayed in square brackets once the record is saved.

The total number of slides can help future users to distinguish between different versions. If you do not have a complete set, you still can say something about the minimum number, i.e. the number of slides you have in front of you.

1.7 Possibility of Having two Entries for the same Slide Set and Uncertainties in Combining Information from Various Sources

At the present stage, Lucerna is assembled from data of heterogeneous and scattered sources. It is possible that two entries have been created for the same set, e.g. when one entry is created from an advertisement in Britain that gives information on set's title, manufacturer and year of production, and another entry from a distributor's catalogue in France that contains information on the total number and titles of the individual slides. As there is no overlap in information, the information cannot be linked with certainty. This is likely to occur for popular topics such as fairy tales, biblical stories and geography. Different sets were produced by different manufacturers. Maybe your piece of the puzzle will solve the riddle!

If you identified a case where two records refer to the same slide set, please contact us via the form on the website, quoting the Lucerna ID numbers or sending the links. If you are not sure whether this is the case, please note your suppositions in the field "public notes" and mark your set in the section "related set" as "possibly same as" (see part 2 of this manual).

At all stages please check carefully to see if an entry for a slide or slide set has already been made. When you have new information to add please choose the option "edit a slide set". When you cannot find an existing entry for a slide set choose the option "create a new slide set"

PART 2: Step-by-Step Manual

Once you are sure about what kind of data you have, entering it is pretty easy.

1. Open your Browser and go to www.slides.uni-trier.de

You will see the Lucerna website.

To insert data, you need to log in (top right part of the website).

LUCERNA – the Magic Lantern Web Resource

Current user: Read-only access
Log in

Home page

LUCERNA is an online resource on the magic lantern, an early slide projector invented in the 17th century.

For more than 350 years the magic lantern has represented and fed into every aspect of human life and every part of the world. It is still used today, both in its original form and through direct descendants like the modern data projector.

LUCERNA includes details of slide sets, slide images, readings and other texts related to slide sets, lantern hardware, people and organisations involved in lantern history, and much more.

[Explore the LUCERNA resources](#)

The Lucerna project is a collaboration between lantern researchers from:

- Screen1900, Media Studies, Universität Trier, Germany
- Screen Archive South East, University of Brighton, U.K.
- The Magic Lantern Society, U.K.
- Indiana University, U.S.A.

[Sources used](#) in compiling the LUCERNA data

The project is still at an early stage, so you may not find everything you're looking for – if you have a specific query or can contribute something, please [contact us](#), we'd love to hear from you.

Access to the Lucerna data

Anyone can search and read the data in the Lucerna database.

If you want to **add** or **edit** data you need to [log in with your Lucerna username and password](#).

Slide showing Arctic explorers

2. At the log in page, insert your user name and password.

3. You are logged in with your user name (see right-hand corner). Click on the button “Slide sets”.

LUCERNA – the Magic Lantern Web Resource

www.slides.uni-trier.de/index.php

Current user: Sarah Dellmann
Log out

Home page

Slide sets

Slides

People

Organisations

Events

Locations

Hardware

Texts

Keywords

Collections

Data selections

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Access to the Lucerna data

You are now logged in to the Lucerna database

This means you can add and edit any publicly-visible data

4. You are now at the start page of slide sets. **First, check if the set you wish to add or modify already has an entry.** You can do this by searching the database e.g. for the title of the set. For this manual, the example is the slide set “Cities and Canals of Holland”.

Search for slide sets

www.slides.uni-trier.de/set/set-search.php

Current user: Sarah Dellmann
Log out

Home page

Slide sets

Slides

People

Organisations

Events

Locations

Search for slide sets

Most commercially produced slides were sold in sets, often related to a published story, lecture, poem or song.

To find a slide set, enter as many search terms as you want in the form below and click the 'Go' button. The more criteria you add, the narrower you make the search.

The Lucerna database is a work-in-progress, and many items are not yet recorded. If you know of something that should be in the database and isn't, please [contact us](#) with the details.

Hints for successful searching

- > Unless you're sure of what you're looking for, it may be better to start with a general search and then add more criteria to reduce the number of results ...
- > ... but if you make your search **too** general, it may take a long time to display the results.
- > If searching by title, the search will (only) return results containing exactly the characters you enter, including spaces and punctuation marks.
- > A 'date' search may be less successful as many dates of manufacture are unknown.
- > A 'keyword' search may not find all sets relating to your chosen subject, as not all slide sets have yet been indexed.

> If your search returns no results, check your search criteria – you may have mis-typed something or chosen an impossible combination.

Enter your search criteria and click the 'Go' button

Characters in set title:
(enter a string of text or leave blank)

Country of origin (if known):

Manufactured by:

Sold or hired by:

Type of slide subject:

Type of image:

Date of first manufacture:
(for a single year, enter the same value twice) between and (inclusive)

Series title:

Subject keyword:
(If you choose more than one, the search will find sets relating to **any** of your chosen subjects, not **all** of them in combination)

Slide images available:

Sort results in order by:

The result lists will look like this:

www.slides.uni-trier.de/set/set-result.php

LUCERNA – the Magic Lantern Web Resource

Home page

Search for slide sets – your search found 18 sets

Your search criteria were:

- title contains 'HOLLAND'
- sorted alphabetically by title

EITHER: select individual sets by ticking/unticking the box next to each item
OR: tick this box to select all the items together.

Then click a button: to do something to all your selected sets.

	Set title	Image type	Usage	Maker	No. slides	Date of mfr.	Series
<input type="checkbox"/>	Belgium and Holland	photograph	lecture	unknown	75-92	in/before 1894	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cities and canals of Holland	photograph	lecture	G.W. Wilson	50	1892	[SPARE] 96
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cities and canals of Holland: additional slides (No. 118-156)	photograph	lecture	Newton & Co.	39	1937	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cities and canals of Holland: additional slides (no. 51-117)	photograph	lecture	unknown	67	in/before 1913	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Holland	unknown	unknown	unknown	14	in/after 1885	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Holland and the Hollanders	photograph	lecture	York & Son	50	1900	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hollande	unknown	unknown	unknown	39	in/after 1864	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	La Hollande: Série 428	photograph	lecture	unknown	30	in/after 1889	[SPARE] 428
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hollande - Série 200	unknown	unknown	unknown	118	in/after 1889	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	The Netherlands: Holland, Belgium, and Luxembourg	photograph	lecture	G.W. Wilson	305	between 1892 and 1908	[SPARE] 173

If you find the set and have additional information, click on the set name and choose “Edit this slide set” on the next page. If there is no entry, then click on the button below “Create a new slide set”. A yellow background alerts you that the current

data are not yet saved. Once you click the “Save” button, the background will turn to blue.

In this example, an entry for the slide set already exists. Click on the set title and you will get to the next page with set details.

5. SET DETAILS

Click onto the tab “Set details” and you will get the detailed list. This list will only be seen like this when you are logged in. It is the main page with information on the set proper; all other fields connect the slide set to other bits of information.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL www.slides.uni-trier.de/set/set-edit.php?id=3000205. The page header is blue with the text "LUCERNA – the Magic Lantern Web Resource" and "Current user: Sarah Dellmann" with a "Log out" button. Below the header, there is a navigation bar with tabs: "Set details" (highlighted in red), "Organisations", "People", "Readings", "Catalogues", "Adverts", "References", "Related sets", "Slides", "Collections", "Keywords", "Check", "Search", and "Create". The main content area is titled "Slide set 3000205: Cities and canals of Holland (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)". The "Set details" tab is active, showing a form with the following fields:

Set title	article etc.: <input type="text"/> main title: <input type="text" value="Cities and canals of Holland"/> subtitle: <input type="text"/>
Type of title	<input type="text" value="found"/>
Country of origin	<input type="text" value="allocated"/> <input type="text" value="generic"/> <input type="text" value="Scotland"/> or type a new one: <input type="text"/> <input type="text" value="alternative"/>
No. of slides	minimum or exact number: <input type="text" value="50"/> (leave blank if unknown) / maximum: <input type="text" value="0"/> (leave blank if same as minimum) notes/explanation: <input type="text"/>
Type of image	choose from list: <input type="text" value="photograph"/>
Usage of set	choose from list: <input type="text" value="lecture"/>

Set title: The title of this set is “Cities and Canals of Holland”. It has no subtitle or article.

Type of title: In this case, the title was found (choose: found). If you determine the series’ title to be your interpretation, choose “allocated”. The option “alternative” allows you to create several titles for the same set (e.g. from different languages).

Country of origin: Choose the country in which this slide set was manufactured. This is easy when you know the manufacturer; if you do not know this, leave it blank.

No. of slides: Enter the exact number (if you know) or the minimum number (e.g. the number of slides of that set that you have in front of you).

Type of image: Choose between “photographic”, “drawing/painting”, “life model”, “text”, “other”. Leave blank if you do not know.

For additional information on these entry fields, click on the red “i” button at the left side.

Usage of Set: This field gives a very general description of the main way this set is likely to have been used at the time of publishing, e.g lecture, religious, recitation, toy, advertising, phantasmagoria. For additional information on these entry fields, click on the red “i” button at the left side.

Now, let us continue to the lower part of the “Set details” tab:

Retail price(s) i	50s.		
Date of first manufacture i	comment: definitely	year: 1892	month: -- day: --
	earliest possible – year: 0000	month: -- day: --	
	latest possible – year: 0000	month: -- day: --	
Series details i	[SPARE] <input type="button" value="choose another"/> Create a new series	series no.: 96	order: 96
		series no.:	order:
Public notes i			
Researcher's notes i	Set is advertised as New Slide set in OMLJ Vol. 3, No 41 (Oct 1892) Set is not listed in G.W. Wilson Catalog from 1891.		
Publish? i	pending	Sort order i	99999
		Slide images available? i	No
		Indexing status i	Partial
Detailed update history i	Created 18:34, 1 December 2008 by Richard Crangle tblset updated 10:53, 14 March 2012 by Sarah Dellmann tbltextlink updated 13:34, 14 March 2012 by Sarah Dellmann tblorganisationset updated 13:37, 14 March 2012 by Sarah Dellmann tbltextlink updated 16:31, 19 March 2012 by Sarah Dellmann tblorganisationset updated 19:29, 20 March 2012 by Richard Crangle tbltextlink updated 19:30, 20 March 2012 by Richard Crangle tblsetself updated 00:06, 21 March 2012 by Richard Crangle tblset updated 00:06, 21 March 2012 by Richard Crangle tblsetself updated 16:44, 1 May 2012 by Sarah Dellmann tblset updated 13:28, 31 May 2012 by Sarah Dellmann tbltextlink updated 14:02, 31 May 2012 by Sarah Dellmann		

Retail price(s): Add retail price if known (some catalogues mention them).

Date of first manufacture: Even if you do not know for sure, please make an attempt to estimate the date of manufacture. Sometimes the catalogue gives an indication, e.g. when the catalogue is dated 1892, the slide set must have been made “in/before 1892”. Sometimes the slide set can be determined “earliest possible” by the subject (e.g. train stations could only be photographed after they were built and before an earthquake or war destroyed them – Wikipedia can help here), and series on Robinson

Crusoe can only be produced after the book was written etc. Determining the date of first manufacture is often the result of combining information from various sources – see in this case the column “researcher’s notes”.

Series details: Some sets appear as part of a bigger production unit (series) with titles such as “English church history”, “City series”, “Keystone geographical units”, “Primus Lecture Series” or “Projektion für Alle” and have a number. If the set is not part of a series but numbered by the manufacturer, choose [SPARE] and enter the number in the next field in this case it is number 96. (Most slide sets we know to date are not part of a series.)

Public notes/researcher’s notes: Here you can enter any other information you wish to add. The public notes will be visible on the website to anyone; the researcher’s notes are only seen to logged-in users. We welcome a short description of the set in the “public notes” field, as this helps non-specialised users to understand what they are looking at. **Do not proceed to the next step before you have pressed the button “Save changes” on the right. There is no warning before you leave the page, and any unsaved data will be lost.**

6. ORGANISATIONS

In this tab/card, you can enter information on organisations; in the case of slide sets these are mostly manufactures and distributors.

For help with editing, click the **i** button. If something isn't clear or doesn't work properly, please [Contact us](#) to ask for advice.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details **Organisations** People Readings Catalogues Adverts References Related sets Slides Collections Keywords Check Search Create

Manufacturer

Order	Organisation	Notes on connection	
99999	Wilson & Co., G.W.		Edit organisation Save Remove
Add a manufacturer (ignore this if 'maker unknown') Create new organisation			
Order	Organisation	Notes on connection	Save new item Cancel
	choose from this list		

Other related organisations (not manufacturers)

Order	Connection	Organisation	Ref. no.	Year(s)	Notes on connection	
4311	in stock of	Wood, E. G.	4311-4360	1894-1912		Edit organisation Save Remove
99999	in stock of	Liesegang, Ed.			Distributed under the German title "Holländische Städte- und Kanal-Bilder"	Edit organisation Save Remove

If you know the manufacturer, choose from the list “Organisation” in the drop-down menu. If you know the Organisation but it is not yet listed, leave blank for now. After working through this manual, you can go to the Lucerna start page, click on “Organisation” and “create an organisation”. You can then connect the organisation to the slide set. Choose “privately made” for amateur productions.

If you have a distributor’s catalogue before you, you can determine the connection as “in stock of” and then relate the organisation = the distributor. You can comment on the connection in the field “notes on connection”.

Always click “save” after you added a connection or changed one.

7. PEOPLE

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL www.slides.uni-trier.de/set/setperson-edit.php?id=3004413. The page title is "LUCERNA – the Magic Lantern Web Resource" and the current user is "Sara". A navigation menu includes "Set details", "Organisations", "People", "Readings", "Catalogues", "Adverts", "References", "Related sets", "Slides", "Collections", "Keywords", "Check", and "Search". The "People" tab is active, showing a form to "Add a related person". The form has a "Person" dropdown menu with "choose from this list" selected, a "Notes on connection" text area, and a "Connection" dropdown menu with "choose from this list" selected. The "Connection" dropdown menu is open, showing options: "choose from this list", "compiler", "illustrator", "images based on work of", "model", and "photographer". There are "Save new item" and "Cancel" buttons.

In the “People” section you can relate people to the set, e.g. if you know the photographer, illustrator or models appearing in the slide set. If the person you want to connect does not exist yet in the drop-down menu, click “Create new person” at the far right – and when you have done this, return to the slide set.

OR:

If the person is not yet listed, leave blank for now. After following this manual, you can go to the Lucerna start page, click on “People” and “Create a new person”. You can then connect the person to the slide set.

8. READINGS

Many fairy tales, lectures, sing-along slides, religious services and life model series, were issued with separate booklets – lectures, songs or readings.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People **Readings** Catalogues Adverts References Related sets Slides Collections Keywords Check Search

i Reading or song

Order	Title etc.	
99	George E. Thompson, <i>Cities and canals of Holland</i> (Aberdeen: G.W. Wilson, n.d.)	Save Remove Edit reading
Add a reading or song		Create new text
Order	Title etc.	
	Choose from this list	Save new item Cancel

In many cases, the title of the reading is the same as the title of the slide set. Again, choose the reading from the drop-down menu, and if it does not appear yet, insert it via the “create new text” button.

Alternatively, if the text is not yet listed, leave blank for now. After following this manual, you can go to the Lucerna start page, click on “Texts” and “Create a new text”. You can then connect the text to the slide set.

9. CATALOGUES

Most of the information is assembled from catalogues. A slide set can appear in different catalogues and be advertised in various manners. Even if there are already entries to your slide sets, we appreciate if you add your piece of information. The process is similar to what you already know:

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings **Catalogues** Adverts References Related sets Slides Collections Keywords Check Search

i Catalogue references to this set

Order	Title etc.	Page(s)	
	Wood's catalogue of slides, optical lanterns, and dissolving views apparatus: forty-eighth issue (London: E.G. Wood, 1894)	34	Edit catalogue
3401	Quotation		Save Remove
	Wood's catalogue of over 200,000 slides, optical lanterns etc.: 1912-13, sixty-seventh issue (London: E.G. Wood, 1912)	136	Edit catalogue
13602	Quotation		Save Remove
	Catalogue of lantern slides: part II (London: Newton & Co., 1913)	607	Edit catalogue
60702	Quotation		Save Remove
	G.W. Wilson, <i>Part II of Catalogue and Price List of Photographic Lantern Slides: Manufactured from their own Negatives by Wilson Brother, Loch-Head House, Aberdeen</i> (Aberdeen: n.d.)	38	Edit catalogue
99999	Quotation		Save Remove
	A series of photographs in the Streets, parks, squares, and Churches of Rotterdam, Delft, Dordrecht, The Hague, Haarlem, Amsterdam, Edam &c., with representative views of the wonderful system of Artificial Waterways developed		

Choose a catalogue from the list and in the drop-down menu and note the page number in which the slide sets appears. If the catalogue you refer to does not appear in that list yet, insert it via the “Create new text” button.

10. ADVERTS

Advertisements in newspapers or the trade press are entered in the same way as catalogues.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings Catalogues **Adverts** References Related sets Slides Collections Keywords Check Search

i Advertisement reference to this set

Order	Title etc.	Page(s)	
	The optical magic lantern journal, volume 3 number 41 (October 1892)	10	Edit source
99999	Quotation		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
			<input type="button" value="Save"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>
Add an advertisement reference			Create new source
Order	Title of source	Page(s)	
<input type="text"/>	Choose from this list	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="Save new item"/>
Quotation			<input type="button" value="Cancel"/>
<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>			

11. REFERENCES

This field records references to this set in texts other than manufacturers’ catalogues and advertisements.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings Catalogues Adverts **References** Related sets Slides Collections Keywords Check Search Create

i Add a reference to this set

Order	Title of reference source	Page nos/reference:	Date:	Type of reference:	
<input type="text"/>	Choose from this list	<input type="text"/>	year <input type="text"/> month <input type="text"/> day <input type="text"/>	main subject	<input type="button" value="Save"/> <input type="button" value="Cancel"/>
Notes:					
<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>					
Quotation:					
<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>					

Choose the source of the reference from the list – and if not found there, proceed to ‘create new source’. Alternatively, if the source is not yet listed, leave blank for now. After following this manual, you can go to the Lucerna start page, click on “Texts” and “Create a new text”. You can then connect the reference to the slide set.

12. RELATED SETS

These fields record other slide sets with a direct relation to this one. The possible relationships are in the 'Relationship' list. Some of them operate automatically in pairs – for example if you link a set to another one as being 'continued by', the other set will be linked automatically to the first one as 'continued from'. This is the case with the slide set "Cities and Canals of Holland – additional slides".

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings Catalogues Adverts References **Related sets** Slides Collections Keywords Check Search Create

Other slide sets related to this one:

Position	Relationship	Set details	
99	continued by	<i>Cities and canals of Holland: additional slides (no. 51-117)</i> (maker unknown, 67 slides, n.d.)	Save Remove
	continued from	<i>Cities and canals of Holland: additional slides (No. 118-156)</i> (Newton & Co., 39 slides, 1937)	Save Remove

Notes on this connection:

The various relations are explained in the "i" button at the top left of the page.

If you wish to comment on or explain the connection between the sets, enter a short comment in the 'Notes on this connection' field.

13. SLIDES

These fields record the individual slides that are part of this set. Each slide has its own database entry, where you can record more details than the basic data shown here.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings Catalogues Adverts References Related sets **Slides** Collections Keywords Check Search

Slides in this set:

Order	Slide no.	Maker's no.	Title	
1	1		Westerkade, Rotterdam	Save Remove Edit slide
2	2		Lake in the Park, Rotterdam	Save Remove Edit slide
3	3		Boerengat, Rotterdam	Save Remove Edit slide
4	4		Delftsche Poort, Rotterdam	Save Remove Edit slide

The specifics of “Order”, “Slide Number” and “Maker’s number” are explained if you press on the “i” button at the top left of the page. In short: “Order” is the order as it appears in Lucerna, Slide number is the number of the slide in the set. Often, the Lucerna “Order number” and the Slide Number coincide. Not all slides have maker’s numbers. Spelling mistakes and other errors in the original title should be left uncorrected. **Remember to save each entry of a slide title one by one!**

13a Edit Slide

If you click on “edit slide”, you can enter a more detailed description of the individual slide – if this is the same for the entire set, you can enter this information via the grey box at the bottom of the slides or via set details (see at the end of the manual: slide check). The “Edit Slide” function is relevant if the style and format of slides differ within a set or if you wish to associate keywords with individual slides.

Slide 5032023: Westerkade, Rotterdam

Slide details | People | Locations | References | Related slides | Collections | Images | Check | Search | Create

Slide title:	main title: <input type="text" value="Westerkade, Rotterdam"/> subtitle: <input type="text"/>
Attribution of title:	<input type="text" value="found"/>
Numbering:	Number in relation to set: <input type="text" value="1"/> Maker's serial number, negative number etc.: <input type="text"/>
Format:	choose from this list: <input type="text" value="unknown"/>
Type of image:	choose from list: <input type="text"/> or type a new one: <input type="text"/>
Production process:	choose: <input type="text" value="unknown"/> or type new one: <input type="text"/>
Colouring:	choose: <input type="text" value="unknown"/> or type new one: <input type="text"/>
Background type:	choose: <input type="text" value="unknown"/> or type new one: <input type="text"/>
Technical description: (use only for generic slide types)	<input type="text"/>
Public notes:	<input type="text"/>

14. COLLECTION

Lucerna can also be used to manage collections of slides. In this case, collectors can link the data of Lucerna to their collection. You can then associate individual slides of a slide set to a collection.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings Catalogues Adverts References Related sets Slides **Collections** Keywords Check Search

i

Collections holding slides from this set:

Record collection data for EITHER all slides in this set
OR just those ticked in the list below

choose collection from list Item no./ref.: Location: Save data

Slide colouring: not recorded Cancel

Date added to collection: definitely year: month: day:

Source/donor: not recorded or type a new value:

Date removed from collection: definitely year: month: day:

Destination: or type a new value:

Condition: not recorded Comments:

General notes:

Slide 1: Westerkade, Rotterdam

Slide 2: Lake in the Park, Rotterdam

Slide 3: Boerengat, Rotterdam

Slide 4: Delftsche Poort, Rotterdam

Slide 5: Oost Poort, Delft

Slide 6: Koe Poort, Delft

We are currently working on a manual that explains in more detail the use of Lucerna for cataloguing or managing collections. Please contact us if you have a question!

15. KEYWORDS FOR SLIDE SETS AND SLIDES

These fields record keywords for subjects featured in this item, to index the item and allow detailed searching of the database. Any number of keywords can be allocated in any combination. **It is extremely important to add keywords to the slide sets and slides so people who look for slides on a certain topic will find the entry to the slide set or slide.** Without linking your entry to keywords, the entry is difficult to search and find!

You can add keywords to the entire slide set (as described here) and you can also use keywords to describe the image content of the individual slides (it is the same procedure, only at a different place in the database. Click on “slide listing”, then choose the slide you want to tag with a keyword, click “edit this slide” and then go to the tab “image content”).

There are two main types of keywords: “subject keywords” and related keywords. The **Subject keyword** is the general topic of the series but does not necessarily appear as title in the slides. In this case, the subjects keywords are “travel” and “geography”.

Slide set 3000205: *Cities and canals of Holland* (lecture: G.W. Wilson, 50 slides, 1892)

Set details Organisations People Readings Catalogues Adverts References Related sets Slides Collections **Keywords**

Subject keywords [Create new keyword](#)

travel main subject Update Remove

Notes:

Add a subject keyword: choose keyword reference **Save**

Notes:

Individual people [Create new person](#)

Add a person: choose person reference Save

Notes:

Organisations [Create new organisation](#)

Add an organisation: choose organisation reference Save

Notes:

exploration
 exploration – Africa
 exploration – Antarctic
 exploration – Arctic
 fairy tale / fable
 figurines
 gambling
 gender
geography
 heroism
 history
 industry
 industry – building materials manufacture
 industry – clothing and textile manufacture
 industry – food and drink manufacture
 industry – iron and steel manufacture
 industry – mining and quarrying
 industry – sea fishing
 industry – shipbuilding
 industry – vehicle manufacture

Keywords should be identified as:

- **main subject** – the keyword is one of the principal subjects the item refers to
- **reference** – the keyword is significant, but not referred to in detail or at length

Remember to save every entry separately.

If you feel that a keyword is missing in the list, please contact the Lucerna group via the form on the website. It is not possible to create keywords for average users. We restricted this possibility in order to limit the number of keywords to relatively general ones.

Related Keywords can be e.g. people, locations. Keywords for **people** should only be used for people *referred to in the item*, not people connected with its production.

In the case of this series, the cities that are photographed on of the individual slides are used as keywords, making the series appear when e.g. people who search for “The Hague”, “Rotterdam” or “Amsterdam” find it.

Cities, towns etc.		Create new location
Den Haag, Netherlands	main subject	Update Remove
Notes:		
Rotterdam, Netherlands	main subject	Update Remove
Notes:		
Amsterdam, Netherlands	main subject	Update Remove
Notes:		
Add a location: choose location	reference	Save
Notes:		

You find additional information on keyword in the “i” button at the top left of the page.

You have done it!

16. The last step is to check whether all the information you entered appears correctly:

Home page	Slide set: <i>Cities and canals of Holland</i>
	Set details Slide listing
Slide sets	Number of slides 50
Slides	Manufacturer G.W. Wilson , Scotland
People	Other related organisations in stock of: Ed. Liesegang in stock of: Newton & Co. , 1913 (item ref. 8LN) in stock of: E.G. Wood , 1894-1912 (item ref. 4311-4360)
Organisations	Main type of image photograph
Events	Usage of set lecture
Locations	Retail price 50s.
Hardware	Date of first manufacture 1892
Texts	Advertised in The optical magic lantern journal: volume 3 number 41 (October 1892), 10
Keywords	Catalogue entries Catalogue of lantern slides: part II (London: Newton & Co., 1913), 607 City Sale & Exchange slide catalogue (London: City Sale and Exchange, c.1909), 242-243 Liesegang's Glasphotogramme für Lichtbildapparate (Düsseldorf: Ed. Liesegang, 1899), 18 Newton & Co., Ltd 1930 (1930s), 414-415 "Beautifully painted, 7s, 6d; Plain Slides 2s each, Reading 1 s. A series of photographs in the streets, parks, squares, and churches of Rotterdam, Delft, Dordrecht, The Hague, Haarlem, Amsterdam, Edam &c., with representative views of the wonderful system of artificial waterways developed by the Netherlanders" G.W. Wilson, Part II of Catalogue and Price List of Photographic Lantern Slides: Manufactured from their own Negatives by Wilson Brother, Loch-Head House, Aberdeen (Aberdeen: n.d.), 38 "A series of photographs in the Streets, parks, squares, and Churches of Rotterdam, Delft, Dordrecht, The Hague, Haarlem, Amsterdam, Edam &c., with representative views of the wonderful system of Artificial Waterways developed by the Netherlanders" Wood's catalogue of over 200,000 slides, optical lanterns etc.: 1912-13, sixty-seventh issue (London: E.G. Wood, 1912), 136 Wood's catalogue of slides, optical lanterns, and dissolving views apparatus: forty-eighth issue (London: E.G. Wood, 1894), 34
Collections	Reading or song George E. Thompson, Cities and canals of Holland (Aberdeen: G.W. Wilson, n.d.)
Data selections	Related slide sets continued by Cities and canals of Holland: additional slides (no. 51-117) (lecture: maker unknown, 67 slides, in/before 1913) Cities and canals of Holland: additional slides (No. 118-156) (lecture: Newton & Co., 39 slides, 1937)
	Series ISPAREI , number 96
	Researcher's notes Set is advertised as New Slide set in OMLJ Vol. 3, No 41 (Oct 1892) Set is not listed in G.W. Wilson Catalog from 1891.
	Subject keywords Netherlands Den Haag, Netherlands Rotterdam, Netherlands Amsterdam, Netherlands travel
	Type of title found on the item or contemporary source
	Lucerna ID no. 3000205 Publication status: PENDING Sort order: 99999 Images available: NO Indexing status: PARTIAL Record created by Richard Crangle and Sarah Dellmann. Last updated 4 June 2012
	Edit this slide set Create a new slide set Add to data selection Search for another slide set Print this record
	Can you help? If you can add any information or images for this record please Contact us

That looks good – but some more keywords could be added! 😊

Now check the Slide listing:

Slide set: *Cities and canals of Holland*

Set details **Slide listing**

Select	Slide title	Format	Image type	Production	Background
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 Westerkade, Rotterdam	Standard glass slide: 3¼ inches square	Photograph	Unknown	Unknown
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 Lake in the Park, Rotterdam	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 Boerenoot, Rotterdam	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 Delftsche Poort, Rotterdam	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	5 Oost Poort, Delft	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 Koe Poort, Delft	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	7 Monument to William of Orange, Nieuwe Kerk, Delft	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	8 Nieuwe Kerk, Delft	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	9 Monument to Admiral Tromp, Oude Kerk, Delft	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	10 On the Maas	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	11 Dordrecht	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	12 Market Place, Dordrecht	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	13 Groote Kerk, Dordrecht	–	–	–	–
<input type="checkbox"/>	14 Municipal Museum, The Hague	–	–	–	–

At the bottom of the slide, you will find a box that allows you to define the style and format for all the individual slides at once:

<input type="checkbox"/>	48 Dromedary Tower, Enkhuizen	Standard glass slide: 3¼ inches square	Photograph	–	Exterior location
<input type="checkbox"/>	49 Old Houses, Enkhuizen	Standard glass slide: 3¼ inches square	Photograph	–	Exterior location
<input type="checkbox"/>	50 Broek	Standard glass slide: 3¼ inches square	Photograph	–	Exterior location

UPDATE SELECTED SLIDES
 EITHER: select individual slides by ticking the box next to each slide in the list above
 OR: tick this box to select all the slides together (this overrides any selections made in the list above)
 Then choose from the lists below and click the 'Go' button to update all the selected slides

Format	Image type	Production process	Background (photos and Life Model only)	Go
leave alone	leave alone	leave alone	leave alone	

Can you help? If you can add any information or images for this record please [Contact us](#)

Once you are finished, log out.

Thank you for taking the time!

This manual was edited in May 2018 by Sarah Dellmann who thanks the various users and members for the Magic Lantern Society Europe for their time and feedback. This manual is published under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#)

